

On s-g-coc-Convergence of Nets and Filters

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Abstract:

Within this study, we use the concept of s-g-coc-open sets to introduce and explore another type of convergence in a topological space: s-g-coc-convergence of nets and filters. Additionally, we look into a few characteristics of these ideas.

Keywords: *s-g-coc-open, s-g-coc-closed, s-g-coc-convergent, s-g-coc-limit, s-g-coc-cluster, s-g-coc-E_f set.*

Introduction

One of the fundamental concepts in analysis is convergence. In general topology, there are two distinct convergence theories that produce comparable outcomes. One of them is based on the idea of a net that was introduced by Moore and Smith in 1922; the other one is based on the idea of a filter and dates back to Cartan's work from 1937. The fundamental definitions required for this study are as follows: according to Al-Hussaini, (2014), a subset A of a space X is referred to as the coc-closed (coc-open) set. The complement of s-g-coc-closed sets is defined to be s-g-coc-open set Al-Fatlawi, (2020). The family of all s-g-coc-open sets in a space X is represented as μ^{gk} Engelking, (1976). The aim of this document is to provide additional details about the s-g-coc-compact spaces in Al-Fatlawi, (2020) by introducing the ideas of s-g-coc-convergence and s-g-coc-cluster for nets and filters, respectively. Also, we use the idea of the generalized exceptional (s-g-cocE) set to provide various features of the s-g-coc-proper functions. $Cl(A)$ and $Int(A)$ for a subset A in X stand for the closure and interior of that subset, respectively (Cartan, 1937). Consequently, in this study, non-empty topological space is defined as

(X, τ) and (Y, σ) (or simply X and Y), unless otherwise indicated. Axioms for separation are not assumed.

Basic Definitions and Notations

We present a few basic concepts that are necessary for our job.

1.1 Definition

A supra generalized cocompact open set (s-g-coc-open set) is a subset that exists in a supra space (X, μ) where there is an s-g-open set $U \subseteq X$ and an s-compact subset K such that $x \in U - K \subseteq A$ for every $x \in A$. The s-g-coc-closed set is the equivalent of the s-g-coc-open set. To express the family of all s-g-coc-open sets, use the notation μ_{gk} (Al-Fatlawi, 2020).

1.2 Proposition

- All s-open sets are also s-coc-open sets.
- Each set of s-opens is an s-g-coc-open set.
- Each set that is s-g-open is also s-g-coc-open (Al-Fatlawi, 2020).

1.6 Definition

Assume that $A \subseteq X$ is a space $\overline{A}^{s-g-coc}$ or s-g-coc- $Cl_\tau(A)$. refer to the intersection of all s-g-coc-closed sets of X including A , which is known as the s-g-coc-closure of A , $s-g-coc-Cl_\tau(A) = \cap \{B: B \text{ is } s-g-coc \text{ closed in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq B\}$ (Al-Fatlawi, 2020).

1.8 Definition

Assume that $A \subseteq X$. S-g-coc-Interior of A is the union of all s-g-coc-open sets of X contained in A and is denoted by $A^{s-g-coc}$ or s-g-coc- $In_\tau(A)$ (Al-Fatlawi, 2020).

$s-g-coc-In_\tau(A) = \cup \{B: B \text{ is } s-g-coc \text{ open in } X \text{ and } B \subseteq A\}$.

1.10 Definition

Designated as the s-g-coc-neighborhood of a point $x \in X$ if an s-g-coc-open set U exists in X such that $x \in U \subseteq A$. A point x 's family of all s-g-coc-neighborhoods is represented by $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}x$.

1.11 Remark

$\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(B)$ is the family of all s-g-coc-nbds of the subset B of X . Specifically, $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}$ represents the collection of all supra g-coc-neighborhoods of x .

We now go over some fundamental definitions, theorems, and observations regarding a net

1.12 Definition

When a relation $\leq$ on D satisfies the following, then a set D is said to be directed (Engelking, 1976):

- (i) for every $d \in D, d \leq d$.
- (ii) If $d_1 \leq d_2$ and $d_2 \leq d_3$ then $d_1 \leq d_3$.
- (iii) If $d_1, d_2 \in D$, there is some $d_3 \in D$ with $d_1 \leq d_3$ and $d_2 \leq d_3$.

1.13 Definition

A function $\chi: D \rightarrow X$, where D is a directed set, represents a net in a set X . Typically, χ_d , is used to indicate the point $\chi(d)$ (Engelking, 1976).

1.14 Definition

The composition $\chi \circ \varphi$, where $\varphi: M \rightarrow D$ and M is a directed set, is a subnet of a net $\chi: D \rightarrow X$, such that (Moore, & Smith, 1922):

- (i) where $m_1 \leq m_2$ then $\varphi(m_1) \leq \varphi(m_2)$.
- (ii) There exists some $m \in M$ such that $d \leq \varphi(m)$ for every $d \in D$. The point $\chi \circ \varphi(m)$ for $m \in M$ is sometimes represented as χ_{dm} .

1.15 Definition

Suppose that $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ a net in a topological space $X, A \subseteq X, x \in X$ then (Moore, & Smith, 1922):

- (i) If there is $d_0 \in D$ such that $\chi_d \in A$ for all $d \geq d_0$ then $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is called eventually.
- (ii) for every $d \in D$ there is $d_0 \in D$ with $d_0 \geq d$ such that $\chi_{d_0} \in A$ then $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is called frequently.
- (iii) If $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ eventually in each neighborhood of x (written $\chi_d \rightarrow x$) then $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is said to be convergence to x . Point x is referred to as the limit point of $\chi_{d \in D}$.
- (iv) If $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is frequently in each neighborhood of x (written $\chi_d \alpha x$), then $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is called have x as a cluster point.

s-g-coc- Convergence of Nets

Other types of convergence in topological spaces, such as s-g-coc-convergence of nets, are introduced and discussed in this section. It also looks at some aspects of the concepts of the net's s-g-coc-cluster point and s-g-coc-limit point in a specific space. We also include some related theorems, examples, and extra annotations.

2.1 Definition

Suppose that $x \in X$ be topological space and $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ be a net .if $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is eventually in every s-g-coc-neighborhood of x , then $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is an s-g-coc-convergence to a point x , (written $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$). The point x is referred s-g-coc-limit point of $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ as the A net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ in X is considered to be have no s-g-

coc-convergent subnet in X , (written $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} \infty$), if and only if each subnet of $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ has no s-g- coc-limit point.

2.2 Definition

Suppose that X topological space and $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ be anet .if $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is frequently in every $s-g$ -coc-neighborhood of x , (written $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$)

Then $x \in X$ is said to have $x \in X$ as an $s-g$ -coc-cluster point

2.3 Remark

Let X be a space and let $A \subseteq X$ then :

i. If (χ_d) is a net in X , $x \in X$. Then $(\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x)$ in (X, T) if and only if $\chi_d \rightarrow x$ in $(X, T^{s-g-coc})$

ii. If (χ_d) is a net in X . Then $\chi_d \alpha x$ in (X, T) if and only if $\chi_d \infty x$ in $(X, T^{s-g-coc})$.

iii. If $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ be a net in a space (X, T) , $x \in X$. Then $\chi_d \infty x$ if and only if there exist a subnet $(\chi_{d_m})_{d_m \in D}$ of $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ such that $\chi_{d_m} \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

iv. If (χ_d) is a net in X such that $(\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x)$ then $(\chi_d \rightarrow x)$.

Note that if (χ_d) is a net in X , $x \in X$ such that $(\chi_d \rightarrow x)$ then $(\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x)$ is not necessary be $(\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x)$ as the following example shows :

2.4 Example

i. suppose that $X = \{1,1\}$ with $T = T_{ind}$ and let $\{(1)^n\}$ be a net in X , then $\{(1)^n\}$ is eventually in each neighborhood of 1. But $\{(1)^n\}$ is not eventually in every s-g-coc-neighborhood of 1 .i.e. since $\{1\}$ is s-g-coc-neighborhood of 1, but $\{(1)^n\}$ is not eventually in $\{1\}$.

2.5 Theorem

Asspose that X is a topological space with $A \subseteq X$, $x \in X$. Then $x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$ if and only if there is a net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ in A for every

$$\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x.$$

Proof: Let A have a net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ such that $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$. In order to prove that $x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$. Given $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$. we can show that for every $d \geq d_0$ because since $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ however $\chi_d \in U$ for every $d_0 \in D$. But $\chi_d \in U$ for all $d \in D$. for every $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$, $A \cap U \neq \emptyset$ hence, $x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$ by theorem (1.17.i). On the other hand, suppose that $x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$. In order to prove that there is a net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ in A such that $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$. Since $x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$, using theorem (1.17.i) we may obtain $A \cap U \neq \emptyset$ for any $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$. Then $D = \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ is directed set by inclusion. Since $A \cap U \neq \emptyset$ for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$, there is $\chi_U \in A \cap U$. Define $\chi: \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x) \rightarrow A$ by $\chi(U) = \chi_U$, for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$. $(\chi_U)_{U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)}$ is a net in A . To prove $\chi_U \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$. Let $U \in \mathcal{N}_{coc}(x)$ to find $d_0 \in D$ such that $\chi_d \in U$ for all $d \geq d_0$. Let $d_0 = U$ then for all $d \geq d_0$ $d = V \in \mathcal{N}_{coc}(x)$. i.e., $V \geq U \Leftrightarrow V \subseteq U$. Then $\chi_d = \chi(V) = \chi_V \in V \cap A \subseteq V \subseteq U \Rightarrow \chi_V \in U$ for all $d \geq d_0$. Thus $\chi_U \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

2.6 Corollary

Let be X a topological space and $A \subseteq X$, $x \in X$. Then $x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$ if and only if there is a net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ in A and $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$

2.7 Theorem

Assume that X topological space is $s-g-coc-T_2$ -space if and only if X is g-convergent nets all have distinct s-g-limit points..

Proof: Assume that X is $s-g-coc-T_2$ -space and $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ be a net in X such that $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} y$ and $x \neq y$. Considering that X is $s-g-coc-T_2$ -space.

$U \cap V = \emptyset$ for both $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ and $V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(y)$. For any $d \geq d_0$ there exists $d_0 \in D$ such that $\chi_d \in U$ because $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$. since $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} y$ for any $d \geq d_1$ there exists $d_1 \in D$ such that $\chi_{d_1} \in V$. Given that $d_0, d_1 \in D$, and that D is a directed set, there exists $d_2 \in D$ such that $d_2 \geq d_0$ and $d_2 \geq d_1$. This means that $U \cap V \neq \emptyset$ since $\chi_d \in U$ for every $d \geq d_2$ and $\chi_d \in V$ for all $d \geq d_2$, which is contradictory. Thus, $x = y$. On the other hand, if X is not $s-g-cocT_2$ -space, then for $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ and every $V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(y)$ such that $U \cap V \neq \emptyset$ there exist $x, y \in X$ and $x \neq y$. $\mathcal{N}_x^y$ is a directed set so put $\mathcal{N}_x^y = \{U \cap V : U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x) \text{ and } V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(y)\}$, Thus for all $D \in \mathcal{N}_x^y$, there is $\chi_D \in D$ then $(\chi_D)_{D \in \mathcal{N}_x^y}$ is a net in X . let $G \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ $G \cap X \neq \emptyset$ to demonstrate $\chi_D \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ and $\chi_D \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} y$, Consequently $\chi_D \in G$ for all $D \geq G$ meaning $\chi_D \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ Furthermore if $H \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(y)$ then $H \in \mathcal{N}_x^y$, $H \cap X \neq \emptyset$ Consequently $\chi_D \in H$ for every $D \geq G$ meaning $\chi_D \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} y$ This is a contradiction.

2.8 Theorem

Let A subset in X topological space then:

- i) A net in $A-\{x\}$ $s-g-coc$ -convergence to x if and only if there is point $x \in X$ is coc -limit point of A
- ii. In X , a set is considered $s-g-coc$ -closed if and only if there is no net in A that converges to a point in A^c .
- iii. Let A be $s-g-coc$ -open in X if and only if there isn't a net in A^c that converges $s-g-coc$ to a point in A .

Proof

- i. Assume that x is $s-g-coc$ -limit point of A . To demonstrate that $A-\{x\}$ has a net

$(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ such that $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$. Given that x is $s-g-coc$ -limit point of $A-\{x\} \neq \emptyset$, for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$. Next, via inclusion. Then $(\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x), \subseteq)$ is directed set by inclusion. Since $U \cap A-\{x\} \neq \emptyset$, for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ then there is $\chi_U \in U \cap A-\{x\}$. Define $\chi : \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x) \rightarrow A-\{x\}$ by $(U) = \chi_U$ for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$, then $(\chi_U)_{U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)}$ is a net in $A-\{x\}$. To prove that $\chi_U \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, let $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ to find $d_0 \in D$ such that $\chi_d \in U$ for all $d \geq d_0$. Let $d_0 = U$ then for all $d \geq d_0$, $d = V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$, i.e., $V \geq U \Leftrightarrow V \subseteq U$. Then $\chi_d = \chi(d) = \chi(V) = \chi_V \in V \cap A-\{x\} \subseteq V \subseteq U \Rightarrow \chi_V \in U$ for all $d \geq d_0$. Thus $\chi_U \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

Conversely

On the other hand, let us assume that $A-\{x\}$ has a net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ such that $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$. In order to demonstrate that x is the $s-g-coc$ -limit point of A . Let $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$, since $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, then there exists $d_0 \in D$ such that $\chi_d \in U$ for all $d \geq d_0$. However, since $\chi_d \in A-\{x\}$ for all $d \in D$, then $U \cap A-\{x\} \neq \emptyset$ for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$. As a result, x is the $s-g-coc$ -limit point of A .

- ii. Assume that A is an $s-g-coc$ -closed set in X and that there is a net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ in A such that $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ and $x \in A^c$. Then $x \in \bar{A}^{s-g-coc}$, since A is $s-g-coc$ -closed set, then $A = \bar{A}^{s-g-coc}$, hence $x \in A$, then $A \cap A^c \neq \emptyset$, which is contradictory. Consequently, there is no net in A $s-g-coc$ -convergence to a point in A^c .

Conversely

Assume that there isn't a net in A that is $s-g-coc$ -convergent to a point in A^c . According to theorem (2.5), if $x \in \bar{A}^{s-g-coc}$ then there exists a net in A such that $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$. We obtain every net in A $s-g-coc$ -convergence to a point in A via hypotheses. Since $x \in A$, it follows that $A = \bar{A}^{s-g-coc}$ denotes that A is $s-g-coc$ -closed.

iii. By using (i) .

2.9 Remark

Let $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ be a net in a topological space X , then:

(i) If $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, then every subnet of $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is s-g-coc-convergence to x .

(ii) If $\chi_d = x$ for all $d \in D$, then $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

2.10 Theorem

Let be $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ a net in a topological space X and $x \in X$, then $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ if and only if there is a subnet of $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ s-g-coc-convergence to x .

2.11 Remark

i. $f: X \rightarrow Y$ represents a function from a topological space X into a topological space Y if $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is a net in X , then $\{f(\chi_d)\}_{d \in D}$ is a net in Y .

ii. Let $(y_d)_{d \in D}$ be a net in Y and $f: X \rightarrow Y$ be a function from a topological space X onto a topological space Y and . Then every d in D there is a net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ in X such that $f(\chi_d) = y_d$.

2.12 Theorem

Assume that X and Y be topological spaces. A function $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is s-g-coc irresolute continuous if and only if whenever $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is a net in X such that $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, then $f(\chi_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} f(x)$.

Proof:

Assume that $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is s-g-coc irresolute - continuous and $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is a net in X such that $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

To prove $f(\chi_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} f(x)$. Let $V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(f(x))$ in Y . Then $f^{-1}(V) \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$, for some $d_0 \in D$, $d \geq d_0$ implies that $\chi_d \in f^{-1}(V)$. Thus, showing that $f(\chi_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} f(x)$, Given that $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is eventually in every s-g-coc-neighborhood of x , then $(f(\chi_d))_{d \in D}$ is a net in Y that eventually

in every s-g-coc-neighborhood of $f(x)$. Because of this $f(\chi_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} f(x)$.

On the other hand if $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is not s-g-coc irresolute-continuous. Then it is for each $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ there exists $V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(f(x))$ such that $f(U) \not\subseteq V$. Therefore, we can we can $\chi_U \in U$ such that $f(\chi_U) \notin V$ any $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$. But $(\chi_U)_{U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)}$ is a net in X with $\chi_U \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ while $(f(\chi_U))_{U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)}$ does not s-g-coc-convergent to $f(x)$ Since this is contradictory, f is an of s-g-coc- irresolute - continuous function.

2.13 Theorem

Assume that $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ be a net in a topological space X and for each $d_0 \in D$, $A_{d_0} = \{\chi_d: d \geq d_0\}$, $x \in X$ is the s-g-coc-cluster point of $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ if and only if $x \in \overline{A_{d_0}}^{s-g-coc}$ for each $d_0 \in D$.

Proof

Let x is the s-g-coc-cluster point of $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$, then for every $d_0 \in D$, A_{d_0} intersects each s-g-coc-neighborhood of x since $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is frequently in each s-g-coc-neighborhood of x . Consequently $x \in \overline{A_{d_0}}^{s-g-coc}$.

On the other hand :If x is not s-g-coc-cluster point of $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$, then $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ in such a way that $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is not frequently in U . Thus, for some $d_0 \in D$ if $d \geq d_0$, then $\chi_d \notin U$, which means that $A_{d_0} \cap U = \emptyset$, followed by

$$x \notin \overline{A_{d_0}}^{s-g-coc} .$$

2.14 Definition

If every s-g-coc-open cover of a space X has a finite subcover, then the space is said to be s-g-coc-compact.

2.15 Proposition

The following statements are equal for any space X :

i. The topological space X is coc-compact.

ii. There is a finite subset $\Lambda_o \subseteq \Lambda$ such that $\bigcap_{\alpha \in \Lambda_o} F_\alpha = \phi$ for any family of coc-closed sets $\{F_\alpha : \alpha \in \Lambda\}$ of X such that $\bigcap_{\alpha \in \Lambda} F_\alpha = \phi$.

2.16 Theorem

Let X be a topological space, then X is s-g-coc-compact if and only if every net in X has an s-g-coc-cluster point in X .

2.17 Corollary

Suppose X is a topological space. X is s-g-coc-compact if and only if each net in X has a subnet that s-g-coc-converges to a point in X .

2.18 Theorem

In the a product topological space $\prod X_\lambda$, a net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ has s-g-coc-convergence to $x \in \prod X_\lambda$ if and only if $Pr_\lambda(\chi_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} Pr_\lambda(x)$ for each $\lambda \in \Lambda$ (where Pr_λ is the λ -th projection function).

Proof

Given that Pr_λ are s-g-coc-irresolute-continuous functions, If $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ in $\prod X_\lambda$, then by the theorem (2.12) we have $Pr_\lambda(\chi_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} Pr_\lambda(x)$.

On the other hand

Assume that for any $Pr_\lambda(\chi_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} Pr_\lambda(x)$ for all $\lambda \in \Lambda$. Consider the following: $Pr_{\lambda_1}^{-1}(U_{\lambda_1}) \cap Pr_{\lambda_2}^{-1}(U_{\lambda_2}) \cap \dots \cap Pr_{\lambda_n}^{-1}(U_{\lambda_n})$ in $\prod X_\lambda$, let x be basis s-g-coc-neighborhood for every all $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, there exists d_i such that whenever $d \geq d_i$, $Pr_{\lambda_i} \in U_{\lambda_i}$. Then d_0 greater than for all $d_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, we have $Pr_{\lambda_i} \in U_{\lambda_i}$ for all $d \geq d_0$. It follows that for all $d \geq d_0$, $\chi_d \in \bigcap Pr_{\lambda_i}^{-1}(U_{\lambda_i}), i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. So $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

2.19 Corollary

For each $\lambda \in \Lambda$ $(Pr_\lambda(\chi_d))_{d \in D}$ has $Pr_\lambda(x)$ for s-g-coc-cluster point if $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is a net $\prod X_\lambda$ with $x \in \prod X_\lambda$

Next, we define s-g-coc-proper functions and present some results that are associated with this idea.

Definition

Suppose that $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. If $f(B)$ is an s-g-coc-closed set in Y for each closed set B in X , then f is an s-g-coc-closed function (Ravi, Ramkumar, & Kamaraj, 2011).

2.21 Definition

Assume that f is a function that maps a topological space X to a topological space Y . If f is the s-g-coc-proper function, then (Mashhour, et al., 1983):

- i. The function f is s-g-coc-continuous.
- ii. for every T_1 -space Z , The function $f \times I_Z : X \times Z \rightarrow Y \times Z$ is s-g-coc-closed.

Remember that a subset of $f(X)$ is termed an exceptional set of f , and it is defined as follows

$$E_f = \{ y \in f(X) : \text{there is a net } (\chi_d)_{d \in D} \text{ in } X \text{ with } \chi_d \rightarrow \infty \text{ and } f(\chi_d) \rightarrow y \}$$

Where f is a function from a topological space X into a topological space Y (Cartan, 1937).

We will present a novel characterisation that is highly beneficial for s-g-coc-proper function by employing a unique set called s-g-coc-exceptional (for brief s-g-coc- E_f) set of f .

2.22 Definition

Assuming that f is a function from topological space X onto topological space Y , the coc-exceptional set of f (for brief s-g-coc- E_f)

set is a subset of $f(X)$ which defined by :

$$s-g-cocE_f = \left\{ y \in f(X) : \text{there is a net } (\chi_d)_{d \in D} \text{ in } X \text{ with } \chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} \infty \text{ and } f(\chi_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} y \right\}$$

We will now characterize coc-proper functions using s-g-coc- E_f .

2.23 Theorem

If X is a s-g-coc-compact and X and Y are Hausdorff spaces, then $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is a s-g-coc-continuous function. The statements that follow are therefore interchangeable:

- i. The function f is s-g-coc-proper.
- ii. For each y in Y , $f^{-1}\{y\}$ is s-g-coc-compact set in X and f is s-g-coc-closed function.
- iii. There is a s-g-coc-cluster point $x \in X$ of $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ such that $f(x) = y$. If $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is a net in X and $y \in Y$ is s-g-coc-cluster point of $f\{(\chi_d)\}$

Proof:

(i $\rightarrow$ ii) To demonstrate that f is s-g-coc-closed, let F be a s-closed of X . Since X is s-g-coc-compact, then by the theorem (2.16.iii)

, In X , F is the s - g - coc - compact set. By the theorem (2.16.v.), The s-g-coc-compact set in Y is $f(F)$. according to the theorem (2.16.v.). However, since Y is a Hausdorff space, $f(F)$ is a s-g-coc-closed set in Y according to the theorem (2.16.iv). F is therefore a coc-closed function.

Then we prove $f^{-1}\{y\}$ is coc-compact, suppose that for every $y \in Y$, $\{y\}$ is a s-closed set in Y , but f is s-g-coc-continuous. By the definition (1.16.i) then $f^{-1}\{y\}$ is s-g-coc-closed set in X , but X is s-g-coc-compact. Thus by the theorem (2.16.iii), states that for any in Y , $f^{-1}\{y\}$ is coc-compact.

ii $\rightarrow$ iii) Suppos that $y \in Y$ be a s-g-coc-cluster point of a net $f\{(\chi_d)\}$ in Y , and let $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ be a net in X . Assuming that the statements (iii) are false, claim $f^{-1}\{y\} \neq \emptyset$, This means that for $x \in f^{-1}\{y\}$ there exists a s-g-coc-open set U_x in X that contains x in such a way that $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is not frequently in U_x

Observe that $f^{-1}\{y\} = \bigcup_{x \in f^{-1}\{y\}} \{x\}$. Consequently, the family $\{U_x : x \in f^{-1}\{y\}\}$ is s-g-coc-open cover of $f^{-1}\{y\}$, but $f^{-1}\{y\}$ is s-g-coc-compact set. There are $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ such that $f^{-1}\{y\} \subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}$, then $f^{-1}\{y\} \cap (\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_{x_i})^c = \emptyset$. Then $f^{-1}\{y\} \cap$

$(\bigcap_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}^c) = \emptyset$. But $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is not frequently in U_{x_i} for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Thus is not frequently in $\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}$, but $\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}$ is coc-open set in X , so

$(\bigcap_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}^c)$ is coc-closed (closed) set in X . Thus by assumption $f(\bigcap_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}^c)$ is coc-closed set in Y . Make a claim $y \notin f(\bigcap_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}^c)$, if $y \in f(\bigcap_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}^c)$ Afterward, there is $x \in \bigcap_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}^c$ such that $f(x) = y$, thus $x \notin \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}$ but $x \in f^{-1}\{y\}$, Consequently, $f^{-1}\{y\}$ is not subset of $\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}$, this is a contradiction. Then there is s-g-coc-open set A in X such that $y \in A$ and $\bigcap f(\bigcap_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}^c) = \emptyset$, also $f^{-1}(A) \cap (\bigcap_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}^c) = \emptyset$. So $f^{-1}(A) \subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}$. But $f\{(\chi_d)\}$ is frequently in, then $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is frequently in $f^{-1}(A)$ and then it is frequently in $\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}$. This is a contradiction, there is coc-cluster point $x \in X$ such that $f(x) = y$.

(iii $\rightarrow$ i) To demonstrate that, for any space Z , $f \times I_Z: X \times Z \rightarrow Y \times Z$ is s-g-coc-closed

Suppose that $(f \times I_Z)(F) = G$ and F be closed subset of $X \times Z$ proving that G is a subset of $Y \times Z$ that is s-g-coc-closed. Assuming that $(y, z) \in \bar{G}^{s-g-coc}$ then there is a net $\{(y_d, z_d)\}_{d \in D}$ in G such that $\{(y_d, z_d)\} \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} (y, z)$. As a result, for any d in D , there is a net $\{(\chi_d, z_d)\}_{d \in D}$ in F such that $(f \times I_Z)(\{(\chi_d, z_d)\}) = \{(y_d, z_d)\}$ for all $d \in D$. According to corollary (2.21), since $\{(y_d, z_d)\} \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} (y, z)$ and $z_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} z$ and $f(x) = y$ Because F is closed (s-g-coc-closed) and F contain $\{(\chi_d, z_d)\}_{d \in D}$

$F = \bar{F}^{s-g-coc}$ is the result of remark(1.16.iv), then $(y, z) = (f \times I_Z)(x, z) \in G$.

G is therefore an s-g-coc-closed subset of $Y \times Z$ since $G = \bar{G}^{s-g-coc}$ consequently, $f \times I_Z$ is an s-g-coc-closed function, making it an s-g-coc-proper function.

2.24 Theorem

Let f be a function from a topological space X into a topological space Y , where X and Y are T_1 -spaces. Then f is coc-proper if and only if $s - g - cocE_f = \emptyset$.

Proof

Let $s - g - cocE_f = \emptyset$. To show that $f \times I_Z: X \times Z \rightarrow Y \times Z$ is s-g-coc-closed function for every space Z .

Let F be closed subset of $X \times Z$ and let $(f \times I_Z)(F) = G$. To prove G is s-g-coc-closed subset of $Y \times Z$

let $(y_0, z_0) \in \bar{G}^{s-g-coc}$, by theorem (2.5) there is a net $\{(y_d, z_d)\}$ in G such that $(y_d, z_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} (y_0, z_0)$.

Thus there is a net $\{(\chi_d, z_d)\}_{d \in D}$ in such that $(f \times I_Z)(\{(\chi_d, z_d)\}) = \{(y_d, z_d)\}$, for all $d \in D$, by theorem (2.20), thus $f(\chi_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} y_0$ and $I_Z(z_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} z_0$. Since $s - g - cocE_f = \emptyset$, then $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x_0$ for some $x_0 \in X$, thus by theorem (2.20) $(\chi_d, z_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} (x_0, z_0)$. Since F be a closed (s-g-coc-closed) set by theorem (2.5) then $(x_0, z_0) \in F$. By s-g-coc-continuity of $f \times I_Z$, we have

$(f \times I_Z)(\{(\chi_d, z_d)\}) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} ((f \times I_Z)(x_0, z_0)) = (f(x_0), I_Z(z_0))$, also by theorem (2.25.iii) we have $f(x_0) = y_0$, which implies to $(y_0, z_0) \in G$ which means that G is s-g-coc-closed set.

Conversely

Let f is s-g-coc-proper function. To show that $s - g - cocE_f = \emptyset$. If not, then there is a point $y_0 \in s - g - cocE_f$, there is a net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ in X with $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} \infty$ such that $f(\chi_d) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} y_0$. By theorem (2.11.ii), there is a point $x_0 \in X$ such that $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x_0$ and $f(x_0) = y_0$. Thus we have the net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is s-g-coc-convergent, this is a contradiction. Therefore $s - g - cocE_f = \emptyset$.

2.25 Examples

i. Let f be a function from R with usual topology into itself defined by $f(x) = e^x$, for each $x \in R$.

It is clear that f is s-g-coc-continuous function and for each net $(\chi_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in R with $\chi_n \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} \infty$, then $f(\chi_n) = e^{\chi_n} \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} \infty$ therefore $s - g - cocE_f = \emptyset$, hence f is s-g-coc-proper function.

ii. Let $X = R/\{0\}$ and $Y = R$ both with usual topology and $f: X \rightarrow Y$ be a function defined by $f(x) = \frac{1}{x}$ for all $x \in R/\{0\}$. Clear that f is s-g-coc-continuous and the net $(n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $R/\{0\}$ has no s-g-s-g-coc-limit, but $f(n) = \frac{1}{n} \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} 0$, $0 \in R$ and $0 \notin f(R/\{0\})$, thus $0 \notin s - g - cocE_f$. Also, it is clear that if $(\chi_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a net in $R/\{0\}$ with $\chi_n \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} \infty$, then $f(\chi_n) = \frac{1}{\chi_n} \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} 0 \notin f(R/\{0\})$, therefore $s - g - cocE_f = \emptyset$ and f is s-g-coc-proper.

Now, we give some results on s-g-coc-proper functions, new proofs by using our exceptional set $s - g - cocE_f$ which makes the proofs much simpler.

2.26. Theorem

Let $f: X \rightarrow Y$ and $g: Y \rightarrow W$ be two s-g-coc-proper functions. Then $g \circ f$ s-g-coc-proper functions.

Proof

To prove $g \circ f$ is s-g-coc-proper or to prove $s - g - cocE_{g \circ f} = \emptyset$. If not, there is $y_0 \in s - g - cocE_{g \circ f}$, then there is a net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ in X with $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} \infty$ and $(g \circ f)(\chi_d) = g(f(\chi_d)) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} y_0$, since g is s-g-coc-proper, then $s - g - cocE_g = \emptyset$, thus the net $\{f(\chi_d)\}$ s-g-coc-convergence to a point $z_0 \in f(X)$, a gain f is s-g-coc-proper, then $s - g - cocE_f = \emptyset$, thus the net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ in X s-g-coc-convergence to $x_0 \in X$. This is a contradiction and hence $s - g -$

$cocE_{gof} = \emptyset$, since gof is s-g- coc – continuous then gof is s-g coc –proper.

2.27 Theorem

Let $f_1: X_1 \rightarrow Y_1$ and $f_2: X_2 \rightarrow Y_2$ be two coc-proper functions , Such that $f_1 \times f_2: X_1 \times X_2 \rightarrow Y_1 \times Y_2$ s-g-coc-proper function then f_1 is s-g- coc-proper function

Proof:

To prove prove f_1 is s-g-coc-proper and in a similar way f_2 can be proved

To prove that f_1 is s-g-coc-proper. Since $f_1 \times f_2$ is s-g- coc-proper, then by theorem (2.26) , $s - g - cocE_{f_1 \times f_2} = \emptyset$. Suppose that $y_1 \in Y_1$ and $y_1 \in s - g - cocE_{f_1}$, then there is a net (χ_d^1) in X_1 with $\chi_d^1 \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} \infty$ and $f(\chi_d^1) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} y_1$, thus for each net (χ_d^2) in X_2 , the net $\{(\chi_d^1, \chi_d^2)\}$ has no s-g-coc-limit otherwise (χ_d^1) has s-g-coc-limit , we can choose $\chi_d^2 = x_0$ for all $d \in D$, thus $f_2(\chi_d^2) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} f_2(x_0) = y_2$. But this implies that $(f_1 \times f_2)(\chi_d^1, \chi_d^2) = (f_1(\chi_d^1), f_2(\chi_d^2)) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} (y_1, y_2)$, i.e. $(y_1, y_2) \in s - g - cocE_{f_1 \times f_2}$ this is a contradiction , therefore $s - g - cocE_{f_1} = \emptyset$ and $s - g - cocE_{f_1} = \emptyset$ is s-g-coc-proper function.

2.28. Remark

It is clear that if X is s-g- coc-compact , then a s-g-coc-continuous function $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is s-g-coc-proper , where X and Y are CC-spaces. This follows from the fact that every net in s-g-coc-compact space has s-g- coc-convergent subnet , therefore $s - g - cocE_f = \emptyset$.

Suber Generalized Convergence of Filters

In this section, we introduce a new type of convergence namely, s-g-coc-convergence of filters. Also, we give examples and theorem about this concept.

Now, we review some basic definitions, theorems and remarks about a filter.

3.1 Definition

Let ξ be a non-empty collection of a non-empty subset of a non-empty set X . We say that ξ is a filter on X if (Engelking, 1976):

- i. If $F_1, F_2 \in \xi$, then $F_1 \cap F_2 \in \xi$.
- ii. If $F_1 \in \xi$ and $F_1 \subseteq F_2$ then $F_2 \in \xi$.

3.2 Definition

A sub collection ξ_0 of a filter ξ on a non-empty set X is called a filter base if and only if each element of ξ contains some element of ξ_0 (Moore, & Smith, 1922).

i.e. each $F \in \xi$ there is $F_0 \in \xi_0$ such that $F_0 \subseteq F$.

3.3 Remark

If ξ_0 is a filter base for a filter ξ on a non-empty set X . Then $\xi = \{F \subseteq X : F_0 \subseteq F, \text{ for some } F_0 \in \xi_0\}$ is called filter generated by ξ_0 (Moore, & Smith, 1922).

3.4 Definition

A filter ξ on a topological space X is said to be convergent to a point $x \in X$ (written $\xi \rightarrow x$) if and only if $\mathcal{N}(x) \subseteq \xi$. The point is $x \in X$ called a limit point of ξ (Moore, & Smith, 1922).

Also, we say that $x \in X$ is a cluster point of ξ and it is denoted by $(\xi \propto x)$ if and only if $F \cap U \neq \emptyset$, for all $F \in \xi$ and $U \in \mathcal{N}(x)$.

3.5 Remark

Let be f a function from a topological space X into a topological space , then (Moore, & Smith, 1922):

- i. If ξ is a filter on X . Then $f(\xi)$ is a filter on Y having for a base the sets $f(F)$, $F \in \xi$.
- ii. If ξ_0 is a filter base on X . Then $f(\xi_0)$ is a filter base on Y .

3.6 Theorem

Let f be a function from a topological space X into a topological space Y , $x \in X$. Then f is

continuous function if and only if whenever $\xi \rightarrow x$ in X then $f(\xi) \rightarrow f(x)$ in (Cartan, 1937).

3.7 Definition

A filter ξ on a topological space X is said to be s-g-coc-convergent to a point $x \in X$ (written $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$) if and only if $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x) \subseteq \xi$.

Also, a filter ξ on a topological space X has $x \in X$ as s-g-coc-cluster point (written $\xi \overset{s-g-coc}{\alpha} x$) if and only if $F \in \xi$ meets each $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$.

3.8 Theorem

A filter ξ on a topological space X has $x \in X$ as s-g-coc-cluster point if and only if $x \in \bigcap s-g-coc-cl(A)$, for all $A \in \xi$.

Proof:

- $\xi \overset{s-g-coc}{\alpha} x \Leftrightarrow x \in \bigcap s-g-coc-cl(A)$.
- $\Leftrightarrow$ for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ and for all $A \in \xi$, $U \cap A \neq \emptyset$.
- $\Leftrightarrow x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$, for all $A \in \xi$.
- $\Leftrightarrow x \in \bigcap s-g-coc-cl(A)$.

3.9 Theorem

Let ξ be a filter on a topological space X and $x \in X$, then:

- i. If $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ ($\xi \overset{s-g-coc}{\alpha} x$) then $\xi \rightarrow x$ ($\xi \alpha x$).
- ii. If $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ then $\xi \overset{s-g-coc}{\alpha} x$.

The converse (i,ii) in theorem (3.9) is not true in general as the following example shows:

3.10 Example

i. Let $X = \{1,2,3\}$, $T = \{\emptyset, X, \{1,2\}\}$ and $\tau^\kappa = \{\emptyset, X, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}\}$, let $\xi = \{X, \{1,2\}\}$ and $\mathcal{N}(1) = \{X, \{1,2\}\}$. Since $\mathcal{N}(1) \subseteq \xi$, then $\xi \rightarrow 1$. But $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(1) = \{X, \{1\}, \{1,2\}, \{1,3\}\}$ then $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(1) \not\subseteq \xi$. Thus ξ does not s-g-coc-convergence to 1.

Also, let $X = \{1,2,3\}$ and $T = T_{ind}$, then $\tau^\kappa = P(X)$. Let $\xi = \{X, \{1,2\}\}$ be a filter on

X , $\mathcal{N}(3) = X$ then $\xi \alpha 3$. Since $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(3) = \{X, \{3\}, \{1,3\}, \{2,3\}\}$, then $\{1,2\} \in \xi$, $\{3\} \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(3)$, then $\{1,2\} \cap \{3\} = \emptyset$. Thus 3 does not s-g-coc-cluster point at ξ .

ii. Let $X = R$, $T = T_U$ and $\xi = \{A \subseteq R : [-1,1] \subseteq A\}$ be a filter on R , then $\xi \overset{s-g-coc}{\alpha} 0$ but ξ does not s-g-coc-convergence to 0, since $(-1,1) \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(0)$, but $(-1,1) \notin \xi$.

3.11 Definition

A filter base ξ_0 on a topological space X is said to be s-g-coc-convergence to $x \in X$ (written $\xi_0 \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$) if and only if the filter generated by ξ_0 s-g-coc-convergent to x .

Also, we say that a filter base ξ_0 has $x \in X$ as s-g-coc-cluster point (written $\xi_0 \overset{s-g-coc}{\alpha} x$) if and only if each $F_0 \in \xi_0$ meets each $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$.

3.12. Definition

Let ξ_0 be a filter base on a topological space X and $x \in X$. Then:

- i. A point x is said to be s-g-coc-accumulation point of ξ_0 if $x \in \bigcap s-g-coc-cl(F_0)$, for every $F_0 \in \xi_0$.
- ii. A point x is said to be s-g-coc-adherent point of ξ_0 if $x \in s-g-coc-cl(F_0)$, for every $F_0 \in \xi_0$.

3.13 Remark

Every s-g-coc-adherent point is s-g-coc-accumulation point.

3.14. Theorem

A filter base ξ_0 on a topological space X is s-g-coc-convergence to a point $x \in X$ if and only if for each $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$, there is $F_0 \in \xi_0$ such that $F_0 \subseteq U$.

Proof:

Given $\xi_0 \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, then a filter ξ generated by ξ_0 and $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$. Then $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x) \subseteq \xi$

ξ , hence for each $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$, $U \in \xi$ thus there is $F_0 \in \xi_0$ such that $F_0 \subseteq U$.

Conversely:

To prove that $\xi_0 \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ i.e., ξ be a filter on X generated by ξ_0 with $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$. Let $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ then by hypotheses, there is $F_0 \in \xi_0$ such that $F_0 \subseteq U$, since ξ is a filter on X , then $U \in \xi$. Hence $U \in \xi$ and $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x) \subseteq \xi$, therefore $\xi_0 \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

3.15 Theorem

A filter ξ on a topological space X has $x \in X$ as a $s-g-coc$ -cluster point if and only if there is a filter ξ' finer than ξ which $s-g-coc$ -convergence to x .

Proof:

Suppose that $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, then by definition (3.10) each $F \in \xi$ meets each $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$.

Then $\xi'_0 = \{U \cap F : U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x), F \in \xi\}$ is a filter base for some filter ξ' which is finer than ξ and $s-g-coc$ -convergence to x .

Conversely:

Give $\xi \subseteq \xi'$ and $\xi' \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, then $\xi' \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ and $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x) \subseteq \xi'$. Hence each $F \in \xi$ and each $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ belong to ξ' . Since ξ' is a filter, then $U \cap F \neq \emptyset$.

3.16 Theorem

Let X be a topological space and $A \subseteq X$, $x \in X$. Then $x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$ if and only if there is a filter ξ on X such that $A \in \xi$ and $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

Proof:

If $x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$, then $A \cap U \neq \emptyset$ for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$. Then $\xi_0 = \{A \cap U : U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)\}$ is a filter base for some

filter ξ . The resulting filter contains A and $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

Conversely

If $A \in \xi$ and $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, then $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x) \subseteq \xi$. Since ξ is a filter and $A \cap U \neq \emptyset$ for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$. Thus $x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$.

3.17 Corollary

Let X be a topological space and $A \subseteq X$, $x \in X$. Then $x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$ if and only if there is a filter base ξ_0 on X such that $A \in \xi_0$ and $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

3.18 Theorem

Let $f: X \rightarrow Y$ be a function and ξ is a filter on X , $x \in X$. Then f is $s-g-coc$ irresolute -continuous if and only if whenever $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ in X , then $f(\xi) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} f(x)$ in Y .

Proof:

Suppose that f is $s-g-coc$ irresolute -continuous function and $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$. To prove $f(\xi) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} f(x)$ in Y . Let $V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(f(x))$, since f be $s-g-coc$ irresolute -continuous, then there is $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ such that $f(U) \subseteq V$. Since $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, then $U \in \xi$. But $V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(f(x))$, thus $f(\xi) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} f(x)$.

Conversely:

Suppose that the condition is holds, to prove that f is $s-g-coc$ irresolute -continuous. Let $\xi = \{U : U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)\}$

is a filter on X and $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$. By hypotheses $f(\xi) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} f(x)$, for each $V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(f(x))$, we have $V \in f(\xi)$. There is $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ such that $f(U) \subseteq V$. Thus f is $s-g-coc$ irresolute -continuous function.

3.19 Theorem

Let X be a topological space and $A \subseteq X$. A point $x \in X$ is $s-g-coc$ -limit point of A if and

only if $A-\{x\}$ belongs to some filter ξ which s-g-coc-convergence to x .

Proof:

Suppose that x is s-g-coc-limit point, then $U \cap A-\{x\} \neq \emptyset$ for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$.

$\xi_0 = \{U \cap A-\{x\} : U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)\}$ is a filter base for some filter ξ . The resulting filter contains $A-\{x\}$ and $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

Conversely:

If $A-\{x\} \in \xi$ with $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, then $A-\{x\} \in \xi$ and $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x) \subseteq \xi$. Since ξ is a filter. Then $U \cap A-\{x\} \neq \emptyset$ for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$. Hence x is s-g-coc-limit point of a set A .

3.20 Definition

Let $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ be a net in a topological space X , ξ is a filter generated by a filter base ξ_0 consisting of the sets $B_{d_0} = \{\chi_d : d \geq d_0, d_0 \in D\}$ is called a filter generated by $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$. i.e. (Cartan, 1937), $\xi_0 = \{B_{d_0} \subseteq X : \chi_d \text{ is eventually in } B_{d_0}\}$ is a filter base, ξ is a filter on X and it is called a filter associated with the net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$.

3.21 Theorem

A net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ in a topological space X s-g-coc-convergence to $x \in X$ if and only if a filter ξ generated by $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ s-g-coc-convergent to x .

Proof:

A net $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ s-g-coc-convergent to $x \in X$ if and only if each $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ contains a tail of $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$, since the tails of $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ are a base for a filter generated by $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$, the result follows.

3.22 Definition

Let ξ_0 be a filter base on a topological space X . For all $F_1, F_2 \in \xi_0$, we put $F_1 \geq F_2$ if and only if $F_1 \subseteq F_2$, then $(\xi_0, \geq)$ is a directed set. For all $F \in \xi_0$, define $\chi : \xi_0 \rightarrow \cup F$, $F \in \xi_0$ such that for all $F \in \xi_0$ take (fixed) $\chi_F \in F$

such that $\chi(F) = \chi_F$. Thus $(\chi_F)_{F \in \xi_0}$ is a net in X and it is called a net associated with a filter base ξ_0 (Cartan, 1937).

3.23 Theorem

Let $(\chi_F)_{F \in \xi_0}$ be a net associated with a filter base ξ_0 on a topological space X and $x \in X$. If $\xi_0 \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, then $\chi_F \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

Proof:

Let $\xi_0 \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ and $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$. Thus there is $F_0 \in \xi_0$ such that $F_0 \subseteq U$, then $\chi_{F_0} \in U$, so $\chi_F \in U$ for all $F \geq F_0$. Therefore $\chi_F \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

The converse of the theorem is not true in general as the following example shows:

3.24 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $T = \{\emptyset, X, \{a\}\}$ be topology on X . Put $\xi_0 = \{a, c\}$ and $\xi = \{\{a, c\}, X\}$

$\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(a) = \{X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}\}$. Define $\chi : \xi_0 \rightarrow \{a, c\}$ by $\chi(\{a, c\}) = a$, then χ is a net in X . Thus $\chi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} a$ but ξ_0 does not s-g-coc-convergence to a , since $\{a\} \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(a)$ but $\{a\} \notin \xi$.

3.25 Definition

Let ξ_0 be a filter base on a topological space. Put $D = \{(x, F) : x \in F, F \in \xi_0\}$, $(D, \geq)$ is a directed set by the relation, $(x_1, F_1) \geq (x_2, F_2)$ if and only if $F_1 \subseteq F_2$, so define a function $\chi : D \rightarrow X$, by $\chi(d) = \chi_d \in X$, where $d = (x, F)$. Then $(\chi_d)_{d \in D}$ is called the canonical net (net based) of ξ_0 (Cartan, 1937).

3.26 Theorem

A filter base ξ_0 on a topological space X is s-g-coc-convergence to $x \in X$ if and only if the canonical net of ξ_0 s-g-coc-convergence to x .

Proof:

Let $\xi_0 \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ and $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$, then there is $F_0 \in \xi_0$ such that $F_0 \subseteq U$. Since $F_0 \neq \emptyset$, there is $x_0 \in F_0$. Pick $d_0 = (x_0, F_0)$, then $\chi_d \in U$ for all $d \geq d_0$. Therefore $\chi_d \xrightarrow{coc} x$.

Conversely:

Let $\chi_d \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ and $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$, there is $d_0 \in D$ such that $\chi_d \in U$ for all $d \geq d_0$. Thus there is $F_0 \in \xi_0$ and $x_0 \in F_0$ such that $d_0 = (x_0, F_0)$. To prove $F_0 \subseteq U$, let $x_0 \in F_0$. Then $d = (x, F_0) \geq (x_0, F_0) = d_0$, thus $\chi_d \in U$. Hence $F_0 \subseteq U$, therefore $\xi_0 \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

3.27 Corollary

A filter base ξ_0 on a topological space X has $x \in X$ as a s-g-coc-cluster point if and only if the canonical net on ξ_0 has x as a s-g-coc-cluster point.

3.28 Theorem

A topological space X is CC-space if and only if every s-g-coc-convergent filter in X has a unique s-g-coc-limit point.

Proof:

Let X be a CC-space and ξ be a filter on X such that $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ and $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} y$ with $x \neq y$. Since X is a CC-space, then there is $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ and $V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(y)$ such that $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Since $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, then $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x) \subseteq \xi$ and $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} y$ then $\mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(y) \subseteq \xi$. Since ξ is a filter, then $U \cap V \neq \emptyset$. This is a contradiction, hence the result follows.

Conversely:

To prove that X is a s-g-coc- T_2 -space. Suppose not, then there are $x, y \in X$ with $x \neq y$ such that for all $U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x)$ and for all $V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(y)$, $U \cap V \neq \emptyset$.

Then $\xi_0 = \{U \cap V : U \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(x) \text{ and } V \in \mathcal{N}_{s-g-coc}(y)\}$ is a filter base for some filter ξ . The resulting filter coc-convergence at x and y . This is a contradiction, thus X is CC-space.

3.29 Theorem

A topological space X is s-g-coc-compact space if and only if each filter base ξ_0 with s-g-coc-adherent point $x \in X$ s-g-coc-convergence to x .

Proof:

Suppose that X be a s-g-coc-compact and $x \in X$ be a s-g-coc-adherent point of ξ_0 . Then $x \in s-g-coc-cl(A)$ for all $A \in \xi_0$, then by corollary (3.17) we have $\xi_0 \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$.

Conversely:

Suppose that $\xi_0 \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$, by theorem (3.24) every net associated with a filter base ξ_0 s-g-coc-convergence to x . Thus by corollary (2.19), every net has a subnet which s-g-coc-convergence to x . Thus X is s-g-coc-compact space.

3.30 Theorem

A filter ξ on a product topological space $\prod X_\lambda$, $\lambda \in \Lambda$ is s-g-coc-convergence to $x \in \prod X_\lambda$ if and only if $Pr_\lambda(\xi) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} Pr_\lambda(x)$ in X_λ , for each $\lambda \in \Lambda$.

Proof:

If $\xi \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} x$ in $\prod X_\lambda$, $\lambda \in \Lambda$. Since Pr_λ are s-g-coc irresolute-continuous, by theorem (3.18), $Pr_\lambda(\xi) \xrightarrow{s-g-coc} Pr_\lambda(x)$ in X_λ for each $\lambda \in \Lambda$.

Conversely: By using theorem (2.20).

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